

2021

WHEN INVASIVE SPECIES & CLIMATE CHANGE INTERSECT

SURVEY OF HAWAI'I NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGERS

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

The survey and analysis described in this report were supported by the NOAA Pacific Regional Integrated Sciences and Assessments (RISA) Program in partnership with the Pacific Islands Climate Adaptation Science Center, the US Fish and Wildlife Service, the Hawai'i Department of Land and Natural Resources, and the Hawai'i Coordinating Group on Alien Pest Species.

Recommended citation: Brewington L, Burgett J, Martin C, Kerkering H, Arnott C. 2021. When Invasive Species and Climate Change Intersect: Survey of Hawai'i Natural Resource Managers. Honolulu: The Pacific Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change Management Network.

Cover image: Maintaining fence lines for upper forested watershed protection and feral ungulate exclusion. Credit: The Nature Conservancy, Hawai'i

This page: The 'i'iwi or scarlet honeycreeper, a species of Hawaiian honeycreeper, is highly susceptible to avian malaria and habitat loss. Credit: Birds of Hawai'i

Back cover: Endemic silverswords of Haleakalā (Maui) are threatened by the twin perils of climate change and invasive species. Credit: Laura Brewington

THE PACIFIC REGIONAL INVASIVE SPECIES & CLIMATE CHANGE NETWORK

OUR MISSION AND OBJECTIVES

Ecosystem health in Pacific Islands is threatened by the independent and interacting impacts of invasive species and climate change. Humans intentionally and unintentionally facilitate the introduction of potentially harmful species globally through trade, tourism, and migration. Meanwhile, climate change presents short-, medium-, and long-term risks to Pacific ecosystems and the communities that depend on them, through the impacts of sea-level rise, warming air and ocean temperatures, changing precipitation, and increased frequency and intensity of storms and cyclones.

Climate change may render certain ecosystems more vulnerable to new species arrivals or expand the ranges of existing invasive species, yet limited research on this subject has been conducted in Pacific Islands. The Pacific Regional Invasive Species and Climate Change (RISCC) management network was formed in 2019 to increase Pacific Island resilience to the interacting threats of climate change and invasive species by integrating climate change science and adaptation with natural resources management and invasive species control, prevention, and research.

BACKGROUND OF THIS REPORT

This report summarizes the findings from a survey of natural resource managers in Hawai'i to establish a baseline assessment of concern about the influence of climate change on invasive species management, compare their access to and understanding of existing downscaled climate information for the state, and identify barriers to success in incorporating climate change into management practices. The survey (Appendix) was adapted from a similar survey instrument developed by the Northeast RISCC (see Beaury et al. 2020)

and was exempt from Human Subjects Approval requirements by the East-West Center Institutional Review Board (IRB). The survey was distributed online through Hawai'i listservs and partners from December 2019 to January 2020, with 59 respondents. The Pacific RISCC is using the survey results to identify tailored research opportunities on these two drivers of ecosystem change that will aid in the development and implementation of climate-adaptive management practices in Hawai'i and the US-Affiliated Pacific Islands (USAPI) region.

KEY FINDINGS

RESPONDENT BACKGROUND AND DEMOGRAPHICS

- Most respondents (70%) were federal or state agency employees with many years (average 17) of experience. Academic, NGOs, and other categories made up 30% of respondents
- Respondents most commonly worked statewide, on Hawai'i Island, and in Papāhanaumokuākea Marine National Monument, followed by other individual Hawaiian islands. Only 3% worked in the USAPI
- Management priority areas were commonly biodiversity and endangered species/rare habitats. Agriculture and game management were least common

ATTITUDES ABOUT MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES IN A CHANGING CLIMATE

- Respondents felt that it is important to consider climate change in setting management priorities, but managing for invasive species is more important
- Almost 90% of respondents are concerned or very concerned about the impacts of climate change on invasive species management
- Over half (58%) say that considering climate change is very important to them in accomplishing their management goals

INFORMATION CHALLENGES

- Most respondents use climate information regularly or at least occasionally
- Climate change information is primarily transferred person-to-person, rather than through the published literature, and it most frequently comes from informal conversations, rather than literature or meetings
- Most people at least occasionally obtain information from meetings and workshops. Twenty-two percent do not refer to peer-reviewed literature at all
- Managers are only moderately satisfied with existing climate products, such as reports, websites, and tools, and although the quality of them is considered good, there are not enough

LIMITATIONS

- Funding and personnel are always limiting factors for managing invasive species, as well as incorporating climate change into management activities
- Participants reported more serious issues with the availability of information on climate change when incorporating climate into management practices

DECISION-MAKING NEEDS: KNOWLEDGE, PRODUCTS, AND SERVICES

- Managers want climate projections that are relevant to their management needs. Desired temporal scales are annual to decadal, and desired spatial scales are landscape to island
- They need tailored research projects and improved communication, as well as a better understanding of uncertainty
- Highest priorities for climate research topics are native community resilience, range shifts/hotspots, and changing extreme events
- Sleeper species (naturalized and potentially invasive), biocontrol, and new introduction pathways are the lowest priorities

RESPONDENT BACKGROUND & DEMOGRAPHICS

ORGANIZATION OR AGENCY TYPE

YEARS IN PROFESSION

Figure 1: Organization type (left) and number of years of experience (right), (n=59)

Most of the survey respondents were federal (46%) or state (18%) agency employees with many years of experience ranging from a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 70, and an average of 17 years. People who work for academic institutions, NGOs, and “other” categories made up about a third of all respondents.

LOCATION OF WORK

Figure 2: Region, state, or county where most work is conducted (n=59)

Most respondents worked statewide (41%), 15% of whom also worked in the US-Affiliated Pacific Islands (USAPI) and/or Papāhanaumokuākea Marine National Monument. Within the individual Hawaiian Islands, participants focused their work on Hawai'i Island (24%), O'ahu (12%), Kaua'i (10%), Maui (3%), and Moloka'i (3%).

MANAGEMENT PRIORITIES

The most commonly-selected management priority area was biodiversity (75%) followed by endangered species (73%) and rare habitats (47%). Many respondents selected multiple categories. Marine resources, agriculture, and game management were least represented and were selected by 25%, 24%, and 10% of respondents, respectively. More federal agency participants worked in endangered species, rare habitats, and marine and freshwater resources, whereas cultural resources were more likely to be managed by NGOs and state agencies. Respondents who were academics were more likely to be involved in endangered species, rare habitats, and forestry.

Figure 3: Current management priority areas (n=59)

Invasive axis deer have cascading negative impacts in Hawai'i
Image credit: Hawai'i Department of Land and Natural Resources

ATTITUDES ABOUT MANAGING INVASIVE SPECIES IN A CHANGING CLIMATE

Participants were next asked to rank how important *managing invasive species* was to them in accomplishing their management goals. A large majority (73%) responded that it was very important, with only 10% reporting that it was not at all important or somewhat important. They were then asked how important *considering climate change* was to them in accomplishing their management goals. The majority (58%) said that it was very important, with another 36% responding that it was important, and less than 2% said it was not at all important.

MANAGING UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE

Figure 4: Relative importance of managing invasive species and considering climate change in accomplishing management goals

They were also asked how concerned they were about how climate change might complicate invasive species management, and all but a small minority (12%) said that they were concerned or very concerned.

LEVEL OF CONCERN ABOUT CLIMATE COMPLICATIONS

Figure 5: Level of concern about how climate change might complicate invasive species management

When considered by agency, the county, state, and federal agency respondents expressed the highest levels of importance in considering climate change, as well as concern about the impacts on invasive species management, compared to participants in academic and NGO employment categories.

Hawaiian native tropical rainforest
Image credit: University of Hawai'i

IMPORTANCE OF CONSIDERING CLIMATE CHANGE

CONCERN ABOUT CLIMATE COMPLICATIONS

Figure 6: Level of importance in considering climate change (top) and level concern about climate change impacts on invasive species management (bottom) by agency (n=59)

CLIMATE INFORMATION CHALLENGES

Overall, most respondents had good knowledge of regional or state-level climate information. When asked how they would rate their knowledge and use, most said they used climate information regularly or at least once or twice in their management activities. This is indicative of general climate literacy, especially given the limited number of products and tools that are available. About 12% said that they had heard of available climate information but never used it, and less than 2% had never heard of such information.

KNOWLEDGE AND USE OF CLIMATE INFORMATION

Figure 7: Ranking of knowledge and use of regional or state-level climate information

When asked how often they used different types of climate information resources to inform invasive species management, participants reported that they frequently learned about climate change through informal conversations (55%). Other resources like meetings, workshops, and symposia, technical reports, and listservs and websites were used at least occasionally by more than 55% of respondents. Although climate information use was overall fairly high, 22% of respondents said they did not use the peer-reviewed literature at all, and 21% reported that they did not use websites and other online tools at all.

FREQUENCY OF USE OF CLIMATE INFORMATION

Figure 8: Frequency of use of different types of climate information resources

SATISFACTION WITH CLIMATE PRODUCTS

Figure 9: Level of satisfaction about the quality, number, and relevance of climate information products

When asked how satisfied they were with the quality, number, and relevance of existing products produced by climate researchers (such as technical reports, publications, websites, or tools), most (50%) participants responded that they were at least satisfied with the quality of what is available. Despite the generally positive perception of product **quality**, 14% were not satisfied at all with the **number** of products available, and less than 10% were very satisfied with the **relevance** of those products to their work. Nevertheless, significant percentages of respondents also said they did not know or had no opinion about the quality (21%), number (28%), or relevance (19%) of available products.

Pu'u Wa'awa'a State Forest Reserve, Hawai'i Island
Image credit: Hawai'i Division of Forestry and Wildlife

LIMITATIONS

Respondents were asked to indicate how severely a set of factors limited their ability to manage invasive species. Overwhelmingly, 81% indicated that funding was often or always a limiting factor. Personnel (78%) followed closely behind. Information availability and access (55%), agency mandates (47%), and prioritization access (39%) were cited as occasionally being limiting factors for achieving invasive species management goals. For each factor, fewer than 20% of respondents indicated that they presented no limitations at all.

Then they were asked the same question, but with respect to incorporating climate change into management activities. Responses were similar. Funding (72%) and personnel (65%) were again most often or always limiting factors. Half of respondents indicated that information availability/access, agency mandates, and prioritization access occasionally presented difficulties. Compared to the previous question, problems with information availability/access were somewhat more frequent when trying to incorporate climate change.

FACTORS LIMITING ABILITY TO...

Figure 10: Limitations of various factors on ability to manage invasive species (top) and incorporate climate change into management activities (bottom)

DECISION-MAKING NEEDS: KNOWLEDGE, PRODUCTS, AND SERVICES

When asked about their decision-making needs, respondents identified several potential areas for greater knowledge, products, and services from the climate information community. Three-quarters of respondents said that more climate projections over a range of scales (such as rainfall projections at the refuge-to-island scale) would be useful. Nearly 70% identified collaborative research projects and better communication between managers and the climate science community as opportunities to support decision making.

DESIRED CLIMATE PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Figure 11: Types of products and information desired from the climate science community

Over 50% expressed a desire for a better understanding of uncertainty around future projected conditions, and how to manage under uncertainty. Having a better understanding of climate science technical aspects, on the other hand, was selected by only 39% of participants. Of the 24% who responded in the “Other” category, participants frequently requested more dedicated funding (rather than research), species- or landscape-level projections and outcomes, regulatory frameworks for implementation, and economic cost-benefit analysis. In a write-in response, one participant stressed the importance of being able to translate climate information clearly to decision and policy makers, in order to set goals for funding and priority actions.

TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL INFORMATION SCALES

Figure 12: Rankings of priority spatial and temporal scales for climate information for natural resources management (n=55)

Having climate projections at adequate and meaningful scales was very important to survey participants. The top ranked temporal scale for decision-making was 1-5 years, and the lowest ranked temporal scale was 50-100 years, the latter of which happens to be the scale of most of the existing climate projections for Hawai'i and the region. For spatial scale, participants identified the landscape scale as being the most important for managing under a changing climate. The largest spatial scales (island, state, and region) were ranked the lowest, which again are the scales of most existing regional climate projections.

When asked to rate potential climate-related research topics as priorities for management actions, respondents most often ranked range shifting species and future invasion hotspots (72%), native community resilience (70%), and changes in extreme events (57%) as high priorities. The low priority topics included sleeper species (34%), biocontrol (18%), and new introduction pathways (13%).

PRIORITY CLIMATE RESEARCH TOPICS

Figure 13: Rankings of selected climate-related research topics and importance for management action

CONCLUSIONS

Natural resource managers in Hawai'i are **highly concerned** about the impacts of climate change on invasive species management, and they have **high climate literacy**.

Information about the impacts of a changing climate on management is typically transferred from **person-to-person**, however, and there is a clear need for more **specific information** and **tailored products** at appropriate spatial and temporal scales.

There is also a need for more invasive species **applications** of climate projections, in the form of **co-produced research**, with a special focus on **native community resilience** and **range-shifting species or hotspots**.

Above all, **better communication** is needed regarding what is available and/or feasible--not technical climate change presentations or access to raw data.

NEXT STEPS FOR PACIFIC RISCC

- Continue to refine priority lines of research, informed by managers, to examine the interactions between invasive species and climate change
- Develop management strategies and actions to these combined threats while strengthening existing, successful approaches
- Create a space for engagement and communication of lessons learned
- Facilitate a network of resource managers, researchers, and interested community members and organizations
- Promote relevant research and develop effective information-sharing strategies

APPENDIX: SURVEY

SURVEY QUESTIONS

1. Approximately how many years have you worked in natural resource management?
2. The institute or office where you work is best described as:
 - Academic;
 - Privately funded research institute;
 - NGO;
 - Corporate;
 - Other private sector;
 - Other public sector;
 - Federal agency;
 - State agency;
 - County or local agency;
 - Other:
3. Please select the region/county/state in which you conduct most of your work. Select all that apply:
 - Hawai'i Island;
 - Maui Island;
 - Moloka'i Island;
 - Lana'i Island;
 - Kaho'olawe Island;
 - O'ahu Island;
 - Kaua'i Island;
 - Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument;
 - Other:
4. What are your management priorities in your current position? Select all that apply:
 - Biodiversity;
 - Cultural resources;
 - Freshwater resources;
 - Marine resources;
 - Forestry;
 - Endangered species;
 - Rare habitats;
 - Agriculture;
 - Game management;
 - Other:

5. How important is considering climate change in accomplishing your management goals?
Select from 1 to 4, not at all to very

6. How important is managing invasive species in accomplishing your management goals?
Select from 1 to 4, not at all to very

7. How concerned are you about how climate change might complicate invasive species management?
Select from 1 to 4, not at all to very

8. How would you rank your knowledge/use of regional or state-level climate information?

- No knowledge;
- Heard of it but never used it;
- Used once or twice in my work;
- Used regularly in my work;
- Other:

9. How often do you use the following types of climate information resources to inform invasive species management? *Choices:* Not at all, Rarely, Frequently

- Peer-reviewed literature
- Technical reports
- Meetings, workshops, or symposia
- Informal conversations
- Listservs, websites or online tools
- Other:

10. How satisfied are you with the quality, number, and relevance of data products, reports, websites, or tools produced by regional climate researchers? *Choices:* Not at all satisfied, Somewhat satisfied, Satisfied, Very satisfied, No opinion/don't know

- Quality of products
- Number of products
- Relevance of products to your work

11. Please indicate how severely the following factors limit your ability to:

- a) Manage invasive species
- b) Incorporate climate change into management actions

Choices: Not at all, Sometimes, Often, Always

- Information availability/access
- Agency mandates
- Prioritization process
- Funding
- Personnel
- Other:

12. What would you like from climate information producers? Select all that apply:

- Climate projections over a range of spatial scales (rainfall projections at the refuge to island-scale, for example);
- Better understanding of uncertainty in the projected future conditions, and how to deal with it;
- Better understanding of the technical aspects of climate science;
- Better access to data outputs for particular applications;
- More info on the appropriateness of data outputs for particular applications at particular timelines;
- Better communication of what information is and isn't available;
- A collaborative research project to help answer specific questions, such as predicted impacts on specific species;
- Other:

13. What timescales are the most crucial to have climate projections for to manage your natural resources optimally? [rate from most crucial (top) to least crucial (bottom)]

- Seasonally;
- Annually;
- 1-5 years;
- 10-25 years;
- 25-50 years;
- 50-100 years;
- I don't know

14. What spatial scales are the most crucial to have climate projections for to manage your natural resource optimally? [rate from most crucial (top) to least crucial (bottom)]

- Field scale;
- Watershed scale;
- Ahupua'a scale;
- Landscape scale;
- Island scale;
- State scale;
- Regional scale

15. Please rate the following climate-related research topics for their importance in your management actions. *Choices:* Low priority, Medium priority, High priority

- Resilience of native communities
- Range shifting species and hotspots of future invasion
- Biocontrol efficacy
- Wet and dry season changes
- Changing impacts
- Sleeper species
- New pathways of introduction
- Changes in extreme events
- Other:

